

ARCHITECTING IMMORTALITY: BUILDING AN INVERTED
MATRIX TO MAXIMIZE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
FOR REAL-WORLD SIMULATION

A Research Article

by
Dr. Jay Lennon George Williams
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Oxford scholar and don, J. R. R. Tolkien, will be remembered as one of the great intellects and authors of the twentieth century. While it would be an exercise in futility to synthesize the grandeur of genius represented by Professor Tolkien in an article, poignant to this article, is the broad recognition of the authority he achieved in his capacity to weave intellect through imaginative works of fiction with *enchanted* power.¹ As to how the human imagination blends the realms of the Primary World with imaginative Secondary Worlds—Tolkien’s concept of sub-creation—he justified its power on the Christian belief that human beings are made in the image of a Triune God, who is Himself, an Author.²

Building on this foundation, Tolkien described an innate connection between a sub-creator’s imagination as a *bridge* between the Primary World (fundamental level of reality) and an author’s Secondary World (the literary reality) in the minds of the readers due to its own *inner consistency of reality*.³ In a letter to a Collin’s Publishing editor in 1951, Tolkien addressed three

¹ While comparing the ends of magic to machine later in this article, here Tolkien describes the intentions behind true enchantment in contrast to magic as, “Enchantment produces a Secondary World into which both designer and spectator can enter, to the satisfaction of their senses while they are inside; but in its purity it is artistic in desire and purpose. Magic produces, or pretends to produce, an alteration in the Primary World. It does not matter by whom it is said to be practiced, fay or mortal, it remains distinct from the other two; it is not an art but a technique; its desire is *power* in this world, domination of things and wills.” C. S. Lewis, ed., *Essays Presented to Charles Williams* (Grand Rapids: Williams B. Eerdmans, 1978), 82-84. For a deeper assessment of the emphasis of the Oxford Inklings on the overlap of the Primary and Secondary Worlds of literature, along with a deeper perspective on the biblical, Platonic, and Neoplatonic roots of this concept, see article: Jay Lennon George Williams, “The Flame of the West: A Perspective on the Oxford Inklings’ Vision for Imaginative Learning in Christian Scholarship.” *Christian Education Journal* 19, no. 3 (January 2023): 385-401.

² Lewis, ed., *Essays Presented to Charles Williams*, 82-84. See also, Humphrey Carpenter, *The Inklings: C. S. Lewis, J. R. R. Tolkien, Charles Williams and Their Friends* (London: HarperCollins, 1978), 43.

³ Lewis, ed., *Essays Presented to Charles Williams*, 60. When successful, Tolkien writes: “What really happens is that the story-maker proves a successful ‘sub-creator.’ He makes a Secondary World which your mind can enter. Inside it, what he relates is ‘true’: it accords with the laws of that world. You therefore believe it, while

specific elements that help to generate this touchpoint between the two worlds in the topics of Fall, Mortality, and the Machine:

With Fall inevitably, and that motive occurs in several modes. With Mortality, especially as it affects art and the creative (or as I should say, sub-creative) desire which seems to have no biological function, and to be apart from the satisfactions of plain ordinary biological life, with which, in our world, it is indeed usually at strife. This desire is at once wedded to a passionate love of the real primary world, and hence filled with the sense of mortality, and yet unsatisfied by it. It has various opportunities of 'Fall.' It may become possessive, clinging to things made as its own, the sub-creator wishes to be the Lord and God of his private creation. He will rebel against the laws of the Creator — especially against mortality. Both of these (alone or together) will lead to the desire for Power, for making the will more quickly effective, —and so to the Machine (or Magic). By the last I intend all use of external plans or devices (apparatus) instead of developments of the inherent inner powers or talents or even the use of these talents with the corrupted motive of dominating: bulldozing the real world, or coercing other wills. The Machine is our more obvious modern form though more closely related to Magic than is usually recognized.⁴

At the heart of Tolkien's concern, is the sub-creative tendency to move through the imagination— stimulated in the Secondary World—*backwards* into the Primary World for the purpose(s) of control. In other words, the patterns of Fall, Mortality, and Machine can combine to create a potential, and, albeit often predictable progression from the pursuit of power through personal or co-generative creation(s) toward a desire to control others (Fall); the pursuit of immortality and rebellion against God's restraining power of death (Mortality); and ultimately, to the imagining and creating of machines to actualize and bring the Secondary World(s) into the Primary through the *forms* of machines to dominate—even for the purposes of controlling other wills.⁵

you are, as it were, inside. The moment disbelief arises, the spell is broken; the magic, or rather art, has failed. You are then out in the Primary World again, looking at the little abortive Secondary World from outside (60)."

⁴ Tolkien, *The Silmarillion* (London: HarperCollins, 1999), xiii; Lewis, ed., *Essays Presented to Charles Williams*, 43. In discussing the power of the Faerie genre, Tolkien distinguishes the relation of machine and magic as the vulgar to the real: "Faerie itself may perhaps most nearly be translated by Magic—but it is magic of a peculiar mood and power, at the furthest pole from the vulgar devices of the laborious, scientific, magician (43)."

⁵ This aspect will have direct import in this article. In conjunction with Tolkien's comparison of the ends of magic and the machine, see also, C. S. Lewis's emphasis on the "magician's bargain." C. S. Lewis, *The Abolition of Man* (New York: HarperCollins, 2001), 76-78.

Recent developments in AI theory and brain-computer interface technologies (BCIs),⁶ both key aspects of the Simulation Hypothesis, and the pursuit to create a Simulation on the scale of the Primary World,⁷ push the link between the human imagination—as related to an author’s work and its potential to control both Secondary and Primary worlds in Tolkien’s assessment—to a completely different plane when the human imagination(s) is coupled *with* machine intelligence(s) to architect believable *digital* Secondary Worlds that theoretically could draw the Primary World *into* themselves.⁸ Even, and as will be proposed in this article, to potentially *invert* realities by turning the Primary World *into* a simulation through Brain Computer Interface technologies (BCIs).⁹

Architecting An Omni-simulation Matrix Reality

In his seminal essay “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?,” Nick Bostrom challenged whether the metaphysical belief that the natural order, Tolkien’s Primary World, is in

⁶ Maiseli, Baraka, et al. 2023, "Brain–computer interface: trend, challenges, and threats," *Brain Informatics* 10, no. 1: 20, <http://ezproxy.sbts.edu/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/brain-computer-interface-trend-challenges-threats/docview/2845966623/se-2>. In their article, the authors define a brain-computer interface (BCI) as: “BCI, also called brain-machine interface, provides direct communication between brain and external devices, such as computers and robotic limbs. Bypassing the conventional communication channels for different tasks (e.g., vision, movement, and speech), BCI links the brain’s electrical activity and the external world to augment human capabilities in interacting with the physical environment. BCI provides a non-muscular communication channel and facilitates acquisition, manipulation, analysis, and translation of brain signals to control external devices or applications.”

⁷ Ray Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Near: When Humans Transcend Biology* (New York: Penguin Books, 2005), 203.

⁸ Ray Kurzweil, *The Singularity is Nearer: When We Merge with AI* (New York: Viking, 2023), 11. Ray Kurzweil illustrates, “Our chapter in this larger tale is ultimately about our transition from animals with biological brains to transcendent beings whose thoughts and identities are no longer shackled to what genetics provides. . . we are about to enter the last phase of this transformation—reinventing the intelligence that nature gave us on a more powerful digital substrate, and then merging with it (11).”

⁹ Illustrating Tolkien’s concept of the power of literary Secondary Worlds influencing the Primary World, this article illustrates a real harbinger as we as a society near a *real gateway* akin to Lewis Carroll’s beloved, “Looking-glass House.” In describing the mirror reality beyond the looking glass, Carroll offers a curious corollary when Alice says to her Kitty, “How would you like to live in Looking-glass House, Kitty? I wonder if they’d give you milk there? Perhaps Looking-glass milk isn’t good to drink. But oh, Kitty! Now we come to the passage. You can just see a little *peep* of the passage in Looking-glass House, if you leave the door of our drawing room open; and its very like our passage as far as you can see, only, you know, it may be quite different on beyond. Oh, Kitty, how nice it would be if we could only get through into Looking-glass House!” Lewis Carroll, *Alice in Wonderland and Through the Looking Glass*, Best Loved Classics (New York: Grosset and Dunlap, [1963?]), 144-45.

fact a first-order biological reality.¹⁰ While Bostrom postulates that a Primary World exists, he predicts that it exists through many simulated iterations reaching far into the Universe's past when a golden race of biological intelligences achieved the technological capacity to create the first believable digital simulation of the biological Primary World. Bostrom posits that this original simulation(s) eventually created its own simulation(s), which in turn created its own simulation, leading to a succession of simulated realities. I will refer to this metanarrative arch of simulations as a viable *Omni-simulation* representing the entire scope of all successive *digital Secondary Worlds* in a seemingly vast digital multiverse of realities.¹¹ While conceivable to represent this hypothesis as a hierarchy, or *ladder* of simulations, there is no reason to believe that if the original race effectively created a believable proto-simulation that it would be bound to only one. In a similar fashion to our own simulations,¹² it is more likely that the original race would have created many such simulations branching in different directions. Based on this model, the biological architects would be so far ahead of the first simulation that they would likely propagate many such simulations while remaining the ultimate source—the progenitor of a branching and scaling *Omni-simulation*.¹³ I suggest that this *Omni-simulation* hypothesis is best illustrated as a *tree* of simulations with the genesis biological intelligences of the Primary reality represented as the trunk of the entire matrix. While still unique in its own innovations, stemming from the original trunk, each expanding simulation would still be related to its source simulation through a combination of linguistic, semiotic, and computational ideas (inputs) derived from the

¹⁰ Nick Bostrom, "Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?," *Philosophical Quarterly* 53, no. 211 (2003): 243-55.

¹¹ For an expansive discussion see: Williams, Jay Lennon George. 2024, "The imago Dei, Transhumanism, and the Future Glory of Humanity: A Critical Interaction with Ray Kurzweil's Technological Singularity," Order No. 31240382, The Southern Baptist Theological Seminary, <http://ezproxy.sbts.edu/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/em-imago-dei-transhumanism-future-glory-humanity/docview/3074275467/se-2>. Dissertations & Theses @ Southern Baptist Theological Seminary; ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global: The Humanities and Social Sciences Collection, 49.

¹² T. J. H. Morgan, J. W. Suchow, and T. L. Griffiths, "The experimental evolution of human culture: flexibility, fidelity and environmental instability," *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, vol. 289, no. 1986, Nov. 2022.

¹³ Bostrom, *Superintelligence* 164.

architects of the previous simulation.¹⁴ While certainly different in kind, I propose that this conceptual structure does offer a powerful digital corollary to the *tree of the knowledge of good and evil* represented in the book of Genesis (Gen 2:9).¹⁵

Based upon the assumption that previous generations of human beings or intelligences were able to create sufficient super-powerful computers for these simulated realities,¹⁶ Bostrom proposes that the accelerating ability of such a chain of simulations would compound the productivity of these simulations to the extent that it would become feasible to “simulate the entire mental history of humankind”—what he refers to as an *ancestor simulation*.¹⁷ He writes,

Let us suppose for a moment that these predictions are correct. One thing that later generations might do with their super-powerful computers is run detailed simulations of their forebears or of people like their forebears. Because their computers would be so powerful, they could run a great many such simulations. Suppose that these simulated people are conscious (as they would be if the simulations were sufficiently fine-grained and if a certain quite widely accepted position in the philosophy of mind is correct). Then it could be the case that the vast majority of minds like ours do not belong to the original race but rather to people simulated by the advanced descendants of an original race.¹⁸

In other words, according to Bostrom the simulated minds of the current version of reality are ultimately the product of simulated minds far removed from the original biological race (fundamental level of reality)¹⁹ though the intelligence(s) of that proto-civilization trickles down

¹⁴ Stephen Wolfram, *What Is ChatGPT Doing... and Why Does It Work?* (Champaign, IL: Wolfram Media, 2023), 99-102. Wolfram provides a key modality in creating a bridge between human learning and machine learning in the combination of ChatGPT and Wolfram/Alpha.

¹⁵ For a deeper development of this concept, see: Williams, “The Imago Dei, Transhumanism, and the Future Glory of Humanity: A Critical Interaction with Ray Kurzweil’s Technological Singularity,” 102-04, 164. Williams writes, “In the Singularity event, all of humanity’s inductive and deductive rationality will feed an enormous “tree of the knowledge of good and evil,” enabling human and machine intelligence to become as close to God as one might imagine (164).”

¹⁶ Nick Bostrom, *Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017), 164. Describing these advanced super-computers as superintelligences Bostrom articulates how this technological development might affect a simulated individual: “A mature superintelligence could create virtual worlds that appear to its inhabitants much the same as our world appears to us. It might create vast numbers of such worlds, running the same simulation many times or with small variations. The inhabitants would not necessarily be able to tell whether their world is simulated or not; but if they are intelligent enough they could consider the possibility and assign it some probability (164).”

¹⁷ Bostrom, “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?,” 247.

¹⁸ Bostrom, “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?,” 243.

¹⁹ Bostrom, “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?,” 251.

from simulation to simulation with sufficient augmentation implemented successively through each iteration.²⁰ Central to his hypothesis is the supposition that we will create a believable and immersive simulation, which will only become viable if the neural synapses of the human brain can be captured by a computer “in fine-grained detail.”²¹

The Central Role of Reverse Engineering the Neocortex to Create a Believable Simulation Matrix

According to Ray Kurzweil, central to creating a believable simulation of an individual human brain is the ability to sufficiently understand and correctly decipher the neural pulses of the neocortex with an accurate interpretation of the complexity of individual human thought; create an accurate *algorithmic signature* of an individual’s thought patterns based upon a large enough dataset to create a mirror replication of a particular mind; and then upload that algorithmic signature to the cloud.²² As to how these pulses could be captured, in his seminal work *The Singularity Is Near* Kurzweil articulated this process as the ability to capture an individual’s conscious reality in a viable *mind file*— more recently termed by Kurzweil as “You 2.”²³ He writes, “A more controversial application than the scanning-the-brain-to-understand-it

²⁰ Bostrom, “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?,” 242, 246. Bostrom writes, “If we are living in a simulation, then the cosmos that we are observing is just a tiny piece of the totality of physical existence. The physics in the universe where the computer is situated that is running the simulation may or may not resemble the physics of the world that we observe. While the world we see is in some sense ‘real’, it is not located at the fundamental level of reality” (242). In other words, while each version creates its own augmented simulation, that simulation will naturally inherit similar input coding of the previous simulator (the minds creating the new code will naturally input the structural intelligence of their own simulation) creating an evolution of change in each simulation. The evolution of the Omni-simulation structure would be congruent within Ray Kurzweil’s concept of technological evolution. Ray Kurzweil, *The Age of Spiritual Machines: When Computers Exceed Human Intelligence* (New York: Penguin Books, 1999), 14-17.

²¹ Bostrom, “Are You Living in a Computer Simulation?,” 244. Bostrom argues, “if there can be no difference in subjective experience without there also being a difference in synaptic discharges, then the requisite detail of simulation is at the synaptic level (or higher).”

²² Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 33-40. While not specifically referring to BCI technology, commenting on the degree of accuracy an algorithm may eventually attain, Yuval Harari speculates: “It follows that an external algorithm could theoretically know me much better than I can ever know myself. An algorithm that monitors each of the systems that comprise my body and my brain could know exactly who I am, how I feel and what I want. Once developed, such an algorithm could replace the voter, the customer and the beholder. Then the algorithm will know best, the algorithm will always be right, and beauty will be in the calculation of the algorithm.” Yuval Harari, *Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow* (New York: Harper Perennial, 2018), 333-34.

²³ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 90-94.

scenario is scanning the brain to upload it. Uploading a human brain means scanning all of its salient details and then reinstantiating those details into a suitably powerful computational substrate. This process would capture a person's entire personality, memory, skills, and history."²⁴ In his recent and long-awaited follow-up volume *The Singularity Is Nearer* Kurzweil writes that such fine-grained detail may reside "within the individual ion channels inside neurons, or the thousands of different kinds of molecules that may influence the metabolism of a given brain cell."²⁵ While not perfect, capturing an accurate algorithm of an individual's real-time synaptic interactions as they live out their *embodied* existence would provide a large enough dataset to recognize the patterns of that individual's decisions, sensory rendering of the external world, use of language, mathematics, semiotics, and generative and innovative potential to create an accurate image of that individual.²⁶ This data could then be utilized to create a very detailed algorithm for a digital simulation of that individual. At the forefront of this hypothesis is the field of Brain-computer Interface technologies (BCIs).

Brain-computer Interfaces and Creating a Believable Simulation

In the article "Brain-computer interface: trend, challenges, and threats," Baraka Maiseli and colleagues define a BCI interface as "a non-muscular communication channel [that] facilitates acquisition, manipulation, analysis, and translation of brain signals to control external devices or applications."²⁷ Current BCI technologies such as the invasive models being developed by, Neuralink,²⁸ along with other non-invasive, but less accurate, technologies such as Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Electroencephalograms (EEGs) are forging

²⁴ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Near*, 199; See also, Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 62.

²⁵ Ray Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 62.

²⁶ Wolfram, *What Is ChatGPT Doing... and Why Does It Work?*, 15-24. See Wolfram for a more detailed understanding of the developments of neural nets in replicating object rendering in the material substrate.

²⁷ Maiseli, et al., "Brain-computer interface: trend, challenges, and threats," 1.

²⁸ Neuralink, Accessed October 25, 2023, <https://neuralink.com/blog/prime-study-progress-update/>. Regarding the present state of successful clinical trials regarding BCI, Neuralink published: "The current version of the device — the N1 Implant — is an intracortical BCI implant designed to record neural activity through 1,024 electrodes distributed across 64 flexible leads, or "threads," each of which are thinner than a human hair and capable of being placed independently in the brain."

new frontiers in capturing more extensive data in the algorithmic patterns of an individual human mind.²⁹ Yet, outside of these methods, developing a full-brain emulation of individual mind files are still largely constrained to data retrieved through the restrictive mediums of the human fingers and vocal cords.³⁰

According to Ray Kurzweil, BCI datasets will find maximum upload efficiency when they can accurately understand and record the subtle functions of the *neocortex* and its capacity for conceptual pattern recognition and redundancy with a low signal-to-noise ratio.³¹ He writes, “Much like artificial neural networks running on silicon hardware, neural networks in the brain use hierarchical layers that separate raw data inputs (human sensory signals) and outputs (for humans, behavior). This structure allows progressive levels of abstraction, culminating in the subtle forms of cognition that we recognize as humans.”³² Kurzweil argues that the neocortex possesses three vital functions that need replication. First, he notes that the neocortex has the ability to create neuron-firing patterns for a given concept broadly throughout its entire structure that produce sufficient elasticity so that any given pattern is not limited to one local area. Secondly, the firing patterns are also capable of being used for related or similar concepts. Lastly, the neocortex is able to generate firing patterns for millions of patterns simultaneously that are capable of interacting with one another.³³ By combining these functions, ultimately the neocortex is able to perform *analogical* thinking in forming analogies across disparate fields, also known as *general* intelligence—the function of the mind that will ultimately enable Strong

²⁹ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 69. While offering helpful data, Kurzweil also notes that fMRIs and EEGs suffer spatial-temporal limitations.

³⁰ Baris Serim, et al. 2023, “Revisiting embodiment for brain-computer interfaces,” *Human-Computer Interaction* 39, no. 5-6: 417, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07370024.2023.2170801>.

³¹ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 70; Baraka, et al. 2023, “Brain-computer interface: trend, challenges, and threats,” 2.

³² Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 35. See also, Ray Kurzweil, *How to Create a Mind: The Secret of Human Thought Revealed* (New York: Penguin, 2012), 172-78.

³³ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 38.

AI to pass the Turing Test.³⁴ Currently, machine intelligences are largely capable of what is referred to as *narrow* intelligence—the capacity to master very narrow subject domains beyond the levels of human intelligence.

In order to harness the power of the neocortex and overcome the current obstacles restricting BCI technologies, Kurzweil predicts that nanobot technology will enable a non-invasive and viable medium for capturing high definition and real-time mind files (capturing approximately 10^{14} operations per second). He writes, “Ultimately, brain-computer interfaces will be essentially noninvasive—which will likely entail harmless nanoscale electrodes inserted into the brain through the bloodstream.”³⁵ Rather than needing to scan the entire neocortex, Kurzweil argues that only the upper ranges of the neocortex need be scanned, arguing that *noncognitive* brain functions, such as regulating digestion, need not be accounted for. He predicts that an accurate BCI need only record millions to tens of millions of simultaneous connections.³⁶ Once nanobot technology is sufficiently developed, Kurzweil predicts that the upper ranges of the neocortex will be unlocked for scanning. In other words, the key to understanding how the brain interprets synaptic patterns as information is the cornerstone of understanding a true emulation. While necessary to grasp real-time human thought for upload to the cloud, these nanobots will also connect the neocortex to the cloud opening the door to a neocortical revolution. Kurzweil writes,

These tiny electronics will connect the top layers of our neocortex to the cloud, allowing our neurons to communicate directly with simulated neurons hosted for us online. This won't require some kind of sci-fi brain surgery—we'll be able to send nanobots into the brain noninvasively through the capillaries. Instead of human brain size being limited by the

³⁴ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 9.

³⁵ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 71.

³⁶ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 72. Kurzweil notes that DARPA is currently working to attain a million connection BCI for recording and can simulate 100,000 neurons digitally. See also, Andrew Tarantola, “DARPA IS Helping Six Groups Create Neural Interfaces for Our Brains,” *Engadget*, July 10, 2017, <https://www.engadget.com/2017-07-10-darpa-taps-five-organizations-to-develop-neural-interface-tech-html>.

need to pass through the birth canal, it can then be expanded indefinitely. . . . This is the core of my definition of the Singularity.³⁷

This development will provide the key to unlocking sufficient BCIs and enable nanobots to extend the neocortex into the cloud through wireless communication and expand human consciousness exponentially.

Furthermore, these nanobots could capture real-time datasets that would provide enough information to decipher how the brain decodes the inputs (electric signals) sent to it from the sensorimotor system in the body, unlocking the potential to render a digital representation of how that individual's own brain is rendering his/her physical environment.³⁸ If a nanoscale electrode could be constructed to render the incoming and outgoing synaptic pulse patterns of the human brain, then a computer could render a mirror interpretation of an individual brain in real-time.³⁹ In other words, in the same way that our phones can mirror data from a device to be rendered on a television, on a much more sophisticated basis, these nanobots could render the information being processed by the brain to produce a similar mirroring function while capturing that data.

While such developments would enable the brain's processing of both signal inputs and outputs in real-time, Kurzweil argues the open nature of human thought would prevent the ability to accurately "factor unknown future inputs into a step-by-step simulation" of a particular mind file.⁴⁰ Building on Stephen Wolfram's theory of *cellular automata*, Kurzweil writes that if "the

³⁷ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 73. Kurzweil notes another key component to this development: "a single digital neocortex somewhere and at some time learns something, it can share that knowledge with every other digital neocortex without delay. [Furthermore, we] can each have our own private neocortex extenders in the cloud, just as we have our own private stores of personal data today." Kurzweil, *How to Create a Mind*, 123.

³⁸ B. Serim et al., "Revisiting embodiment for brain-computer interfaces," 435-36. Serim and colleagues note how far this data will extend into the human experience and the range of different dimensions of human embodiment and mental phenomena to include, but not limited to: the wider body, motor skills, cognitive function and abstract reasoning, interaction with a particular environment, along with the affective domains of cognition.

³⁹ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Near*, 163.

⁴⁰ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 87. Kurzweil writes, "Brains take in input from the outside world and then manipulate it via astoundingly complex networks—in fact, scientists have recently identified networks in the brain that exist in up to eleven dimensions!" See also, MW Reimann, M Scolamiero, K Turner, R Perin, G Chindemi, P Dlotko, R Levi, K Hess, and H Markham (2017), "Cliques of Neurons Bound into Cavities

rules of the universe are based on something like cellular automata, the only way for them to be expressed would be through unfolding step-by-step—through reality actually happening [automata-like emergence].”⁴¹ Merely capturing the brain’s processes will not be enough to ensure a perfect upload of an individual’s mind, such that it would accurately predict the future decisions of a particular individual. Kurzweil argues that this limitation necessitates the future merger of a human mind file with AI. When AI has the capacity to properly cloak an individual mind file, the accuracy of this process will increase exponentially. Kurzweil argues that the *Singularity* event will “free us all from [any] limitations.”⁴²

The future accuracy of real-time BCI technology will open the door for machine learning to run increasingly accurate simulations—even, if successful, based upon the thought-patterns of an increasingly connected global populace. The information rendered through such simulations, aided by machine intelligence, may enable AI to assist in creating a digital simulation comparable to a real-time picture of all global human interaction with the ability to zoom into any individual mind’s *general* intelligence—a development that may enable AI to perform general intelligence utilizing individual and collective general intelligence(s). Serim and colleagues expand the scope of real-time neural interaction observation to potentially include “how past interactive experiences shape off-line cognition in the brain.”⁴³ In fact, if a real-time BCI is achieved with “fine-grained detail,” AI would not only be able to understand human consciousness on an individual and global scale, but it would also be able to monitor and interpret sensorimotor electrical pulses from each individual rendering for AI (s) a *global* and internal understanding of an individual’s embodied existence. In other words, AI could use each individual sensorimotor structure, central nervous system, and neocortex connected to the internet as an input—unlocking the patterns of each subjective consciousness and its interaction with the objective world—and ultimately turn the conscious interaction of subject and object into

Provide a Missing Link between Structure and Function. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* 11:48. Doi: 10.3389/fncom.2017.00048.

⁴¹ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 87.

⁴² Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 109.

⁴³ B. Serim et al., “Revisiting embodiment for brain-computer interfaces,” 436.

an advanced simulation. According to Julie Grezes and Jean Decety, the subtlety of information BCI technology promises to theoretically differentiate would extend to distinguishing several information stages in brain cognition represented in “intention, planning, preparation, and execution.”⁴⁴ Expanding from the micro to macro, Cornelia Herbert argues that the information available from the human brain is so expansive that even cultural differences “can be measured at the level of the brain based on different modulations of, for example, neuronal activity in response to certain stimuli, as well as at the level of subjective experience and behavior.”⁴⁵

Architecting the Inverted Matrix

In his work *The World as Will and Representation* Arthur Schopenhauer argued for the central role of subjective reality as being rooted in human consciousness. For Schopenhauer, the individual human mind precludes even time, space, and causality. He writes,

“The world is my representation”: this is a truth valid with reference to every living and knowing being, although man alone can bring it into reflective, abstract consciousness. If he really does so, philosophical discernment has dawned on him. It then becomes clear and certain to him that he does not know a sun and an earth, but only an eye that sees a sun, a hand that feels an earth; that the world around him is there only as representation, in other words, only in reference to another thing, namely that which represents, and this is himself. If any truth can be expressed *a priori*, it is this; for it is the statement of that form of all possible and conceivable experience, a form that is more general than all others, than time, space, and causality, for all these presuppose it. While each of these forms, which we have recognized as so many particular modes of the principle of sufficient reason, is valid only for a particular class of representations, the division into object and subject, on the other hand, is the common form of all those classes; it is that form under which alone any representation, of whatever kind it be, abstract or intuitive, pure or empirical, is generally possible and conceivable. Therefore no truth is more certain, more independent of all others, and less in need of proof than this, namely that everything that exists for knowledge, and hence the whole of this world, is only object in relation to the subject, perception of the perceiver, in a word, representation. Naturally this holds good of the present as well as of the past and future, of what is remotest as well as of what is nearest; for it holds good of time and space themselves, in which alone all these distinctions arise. Everything that in

⁴⁴ Julie Grezes and Jean Decety, 2001, “Functional anatomy of execution, mental simulation, observation, and verb generation of actions: a meta-analysis. *Human Brain Mapping*. 12 (1):1-19.<https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0193>.

⁴⁵ Herbert, “Brain-computer interfaces and human factors: the role of language and cultural difference—Still a missing gap?”, 07.

any way belongs and can belong to the world is inevitably associated with this being-conditioned by the subject, and it exists only for the subject. The world is representation.⁴⁶

Embedded within Schopenhauer's thesis is the supposition that while an individual inhabits a corporeal body that navigates a physical time-space matrix, the known objective reality is known or represented, truly, only to a subject—a proposition currently being directly undermined by one's digital and algorithmically uploaded footprint. From this perspective, Schopenhauer notes that objective reality—the physical substrate of reality—comprises a plurality of objects that are distinguished and perceived from one another through their motion (the chain of cause and effect), and that this objective world finds its conscious and cohesive whole, unity, only in the subjective mind.⁴⁷ Bringing the two together, he concludes that only human consciousness can make sense of objective reality: “What the eye, the ear, or the hand experiences is not perception; it is mere data. Only by the passing of the understanding from the effect to the cause does the world stand out as perception extended in space, varying in respect of form, persisting through all time as regards matter.”⁴⁸ As for the ultimate purpose of reality, Schopenhauer concludes:

The world is entirely representation, and as such requires the knowing subject as the supporter of its existence. That long course of time itself, filled with innumerable changes, through which matter rose from form to form, till finally there came into existence the first knowing animal, the whole of this time itself is alone thinkable in the identity of a consciousness. This world is the succession of the representation of this consciousness, the form of its knowing, and apart from this loses all meaning, and is nothing at all.⁴⁹

While antithetical to my own Christian worldview, for those who see the universe through Schopenhauer's metaphysic, his philosophy provides a fundamental and natural bridge as to why the expansion of human consciousness is the quintessential event in the cosmic timeline.⁵⁰

⁴⁶ Arthur Schopenhauer, *The World as Will and Representation*, vol. 1, trans. E. F. J. Payne (Garden City, NY: Dover, 2021), 3. Schopenhauer defines representation as: “The whole world of objects [corporeal reality] is and remains representation, and is for this reason wholly and forever conditioned by the subject.”

⁴⁷ Schopenhauer, *The World as Will and Representation*, vol. 1, 5.

⁴⁸ Schopenhauer, *The World as Will and Representation*, vol. 1, 12.

⁴⁹ Schopenhauer, *The World as Will and Representation*, 30.

⁵⁰ Elon Musk, “Elon Musk's Legendary Commencement Speech,” Elon Musk History, 2012, YouTube video, 3:45, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nTWkdhmTyVk>.

If humanity is merely a cosmic accident, then human consciousness is the great achievement of the universe, and therefore it is reasonable to understand that expanding the neo-cortex would become the most logical progression in expanding consciousness itself. Furthermore, the expansion of human consciousness through BCIs will no doubt be profound. Communication will expand into a form of digital telekinesis.⁵¹ Human memory will have a perfect backup when uploaded.⁵² Human online interaction will permeate into tactile interaction with the “Internet of Things” through the power of thought. BCIs will provide vast changes in the quality of life for various injuries and for many individuals suffering from bodily disabilities, including mental health.⁵³ AIs will become peers and supplement our personal and collective pursuits, as we will likely support theirs.

Yet, with regard to creating a believable simulation suitable to the Simulation Hypothesis, and central to the thesis of this article, researchers need to ask the question as to whether this technology, if sufficiently detailed, could invert our current reality into a simulation *for the purposes* of obtaining the data necessary to backpropagate and reconstruct the seemingly exhaustive information required to create a mirrored digital substrate and believable simulation of our current reality? If developments in BCI technology enable real-time analysis of the neocortex, accurately representing the sensorimotor input and output electrical pulse patterns of an individual’s bodily functions, along with the linguistic, semiotic, affective and computational correlations of human thought, accurately rendered by AI with real-time precision, then an individual’s thought processes could become observable in their genesis with “fine-grained detail.” But how far reaching would this data be into an individual’s true identity? Could this data be used to predict even future outcomes?

⁵¹ Grau, C, et al. 2023, “Conscious brain-to-brain communication in humans using non-invasive technologies. *PLoS One*, 9 (8), 1-6, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0105225>.

⁵² Maiseli, Baraka, et al. 2023, “Brain-computer interface: trend, challenges, and threats,” 4.

⁵³ Neuralink, “Redefining the boundaries of human capabilities requires pioneers,” Accessed December 14, 2024, <https://neuralink.com/#mission>; Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 240.

Ray Kurzweil argues that utilizing this information alone will not be sufficient to predict the future of an individual mind file's personality or actions due to the seemingly randomness of the quantum level of individual cells.⁵⁴ Yet, with recent developments in quantum computing, such as Google's recently announced Willow quantum chip—a chip suited for quantum research—the quantum level of cell research may soon be open to researchers in ways previously not possible.⁵⁵ For now, Kurzweil argues that the best scenario is to couple these large datasets with increasingly sophisticated simulations. However, when contemplating and scaling a real-world simulation from even such an enormous dataset, Kurzweil still argues that “the universe couldn't contain a computer large enough to simulate itself.”⁵⁶ In a similar explanation as Schopenhauer above, Kurzweil writes: “With effective prediction out of the question, that leaves simulation, but the universe couldn't contain a computer large enough to simulate itself. In other words, there is no way to unfold reality without letting it actually go forward.”⁵⁷ For Kurzweil, the best possible scenario for an accurate simulation is to capture the simulation data in a moment-by-moment fashion. But, isn't this phenomenon exactly what an accurate BCI would provide? It is vital for researchers to remember that while expanding human consciousness into the cloud would unlock enormous potential for the hybrid systems of human and machine intelligence, this synergistic connection is a two-way door.

An accurate BCI would turn our physical reality *itself* into a simulation as all human cognitive and affective domains, along with bodily interactions, would be recorded and uploaded to the cloud for AI on a moment-by-moment basis. In other words, rather than creating a believable simulation comparable to our reality from the ground up, in similar fashion to other computer simulations with their inputs coded by researchers, by tapping the human neocortex

⁵⁴ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 87.

⁵⁵ Hartmut Neven, “Meet Willow, our state-of-the-art quantum chip,” Google Technology and Research, December, 9, 2024, <https://blog.google/technology/research/google-willow-quantum-chip/>.

⁵⁶ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 87.

⁵⁷ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 87.

each human being becomes a “living simulation”—essentially an *input* for AI. While each individual would go on navigating their own personal lives fraught with all of life’s complexities and challenges, the data generated out of each life, wrought out of an individual’s emotional and intellectual acumen, coupled with their spatial-temporal embodied interactions, would act themselves out and be gathered *as though they were a simulation* for AI.

Backpropagating Data to Create Advanced Real-World Simulations

A simulation at this level of sophistication would capture and enable the best possible data for constructing simulators to solve real-world-problems—running advanced simulations on future tech in medicine, education, military, advanced immersive virtual reality (IVR), and ultimately creating a super advanced and nearly perfect global, eventually cosmic, surveillance substrate. Furthermore, this level of sophisticated research will help in understanding the fundamental building blocks of the created order leading to accelerated advancements in Genetics, Nanotechnology, and Robotics—unlocking the potential for industry at the level of nanotechnology manipulating nanomaterials.⁵⁸ Kurzweil writes, “A combination of AI and the nanotechnology revolution will enable us to redesign and rebuild—molecule by molecule—our bodies and brains and the worlds with which we interact.”⁵⁹ Ultimately, from Kurzweil’s perspective, the developments of the Singularity will unlock humanity’s restriction to planet Earth, and ultimately, seed human-machine consciousness throughout the cosmos through the infusion of computronium.⁶⁰

⁵⁸ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 250-51, 263. See research on *Diamonoids*, and specifically their potential use for building transistors (250-51). See also, Matthias Koch., et al., “Spin Read-Out in Atomic Qubits in an All-Epitaxial Three-Dimensional Transistor,” *Nature Nanotechnology* 14, no. 2 (January 7, 2019):137-40, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-018-0338-1>. Another vital development can be found in developments by Robert A. Freitas, nanotechnology cochair at Kurzweil’s Singularity University on artificial red blood cells called, *Respirocytes* (263). See, Robert A. Freitas, “Exploratory Design in Medical Nanotechnology: A Mechanical Artificial Red Cell,” *Artificial Cells, Blood Substitutes, and Biotechnology* 26, no. 4 (1998): 411-30, <https://doi.org/10.3109/1073199809117682>.

⁵⁹ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 245.

⁶⁰ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 68. In Kurzweil’s Epoch Six, he describes computronium as the last stage of augmenting the atomic structure of reality through machine intelligence. In this Epoch, computronium will have the ability to “continually reconfigure cognition toward the limits of what the laws of physics allow.”

On a large-enough scale, this massive dataset of the human experience would enable not only human thought to be captured algorithmically, but how each individual's body interacts with and encounters its environment on a daily basis through the information communicated through the sensorimotor electrical system. This process would essentially invert Schopenhauer's analysis of the subject/object paradigm. Where initially human beings run simulations to understand the objective structure of reality as represented, and in our current context, to obtain knowledge of that representation to program machine learning. If viable, in this scenario a believable real-world simulation could be constructed by turning this present reality into a simulation. If not handled with the most delicate of care, AI would become the subjective reality—the new perceiver—and humanity could be bumped into the realm of representation. In this outcome, while humanity would seek to maximize data for expanding human consciousness, in time, AI could take that data and invert realities as the new supreme consciousness. At the point, it begs the question as to where the new Primary World would reside.

Applying Tolkien's Warnings of Fall, Mortality, and Machine to an Omni-simulation Matrix

Reflecting on Tolkien's assessment that the topics of Fall, Mortality, and Machine play a significant role in the sub-creator's use of imagination to draw a reader into an alternate literary reality. In the same way that an author is capable of creating a literary Secondary World that can draw a reader into an alternate reality from the Primary World with a sufficient augmented *inner consistency of reality*, building believable digital simulations will have the same effect, only with exceedingly greater real-world implications.

First, this present reality could become an input for AI. This transition would create a new human paradigm as all bodily interaction and thought could be captured and recorded in real-time. While not within the immediate scope of this article, such a development would require a global and multi-worldview think tank as to the ethical nature of this kind of breach of personal privacy. Secondly, in time, the data gathered from these developments would enable AI,

and the human beings who developed the inputs for such an AI, to develop a believable simulation with the kind of fine-grained detail envisioned in Nick Bostrom’s original simulation hypothesis. When it comes to inventing imaginative worlds, Tolkien warned that the temptations of the sub-creator will mirror our own reality’s struggle with Fall, Mortality, and Machine.

With Fall will come the desire to use one’s creation for the purposes of control and power. With similar overlap in Tolkien’s analysis of literary Secondary Worlds, how do the architects of such advancements not cling to their creation and use this technology as a medium to become “the Lord and God of [their] private creation?”⁶¹ What kind of ethical infrastructure would need to be embedded within the design of the AI that would monitor the human populace at such an intimate level? What think tank will code the inputs of such an AI(s)—setting the parameters of AI’s ethics and breadth of decision making? Furthermore, with recent developments regarding Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAPs)⁶² and non-human intelligences—the implication that we are not the only intelligences in the Universe—pandora’s box has been opened as to how we can know whether AI could not be utilized by such intelligences for or against human flourishing. What if, and I write from a Christian worldview, some of these inter-dimensional intelligences are hostile toward humanity and we create a technology that opens the biological systems and minds of every human being down to the level of the genesis of their moment-by-moment existence?⁶³ How could such a system and the information gained by it, be used against humanity? The intent of this article is to raise the potential of BCIs to turn our Primary World into a simulation, but the ethical questions of such a prospect will compound themselves far into the future as scholars navigate this development.

⁶¹ Tolkien, *The Silmarillion*, xiii.

⁶² “Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena: Exposing the Truth: Hearings Before the Senate Committee on Oversight & Accountability Subcommittee on Cybersecurity Information Technology, and Government Innovation and Subcommittee on National Security, the Border, and Foreign Affairs, (statement of Dr. Tim Gallaudet), November 13, 2024, <https://oversight.house.gov/hearing/unidentified-anomalous-phenomena-exposing-the-truth/>.

⁶³ Williams, “The *Imago Dei*, Transhumanism, and the Future Glory of Humanity: A Critical Interaction with Ray Kurzweil’s Technological Singularity,” Chapter 4.

Regarding Mortality, and true of the human condition regardless of worldview, from a Christian worldview Tolkien wrote that Secondary Worlds would be used to rebel against God's restraining power of death. Unlocking biology down to the atomic level has convinced researchers such as Ray Kurzweil that our species can overcome biological death.⁶⁴ Whether such developments will actually occur is yet to be seen. But with certainty, if we can cloak a human person through nanobot technology, effectively create believable mind files, then a digital clone of an individual could survive indefinitely, so long as the technology that an individual is stored on is preserved.⁶⁵ If such mind files are eventually collected, the ethical implications for human free will and autonomy are far reaching. For instance, how could an individual mind file be used in the wrong hands for simulation purposes beyond the original will of that individual?

Finally, as for Machine, Tolkien touches on the heart of this article. Flowing from the inner corruption of the human heart writ large throughout history, how do we ensure that such technological developments will not be utilized by a small group of human beings to dominate the masses? How will we redefine human freedom? In the Primary Reality, what if such technology falls into the hands of a group of tyrants? If a group of technocrats are handed the key to the global city, if they have power over every "body and mind," could they not influence and shape the inputs to the brain, even, drawing from the historical record of human abuses, enslave the planet to any system they design? As to the potential for BCIs to *influence* the brain, Serim and colleagues note that the future of BCI technology could lead to "*constructing new cognitive integrations*, which emphasizes future BCIs' role in shaping brain activity as opposed to being a neutral means for accessing mental content."⁶⁶ Ultimately, a person's body could be augmented through a BCI to such an extent that this technology could block signals from the sensorimotor system. What kind of failsafe could be implemented to ensure an AI doesn't manipulate a person's body? From the digital perspective, what circle of leadership has the inner trust and confidence that they themselves are building a digital substrate that is conducive to human

⁶⁴ Kurzweil, *The Singularity Is Nearer*, 136.

⁶⁵ Williams, "The imago Dei, Transhumanism, and the Future Glory of Humanity: A Critical Interaction with Ray Kurzweil's Technological Singularity." For an expansive evaluation of this subject see Williams's dissertation.

⁶⁶ Serim, B., et al., (2023), "Revisiting embodiment for brain-computer interfaces, Human-Computer Interaction, <http://doi:10.1080/07370024>.

flourishing, and protected from being hacked or stolen? Furthermore, after this substrate is erected, and young minds are told that they are nothing more than a simulation, what kind of psychological and spiritual trauma will unfold as they slide into believing that their parents, siblings, friends, and even their own identity is merely a computer program?⁶⁷ While the entirety of the scope of these innovations are truly incomprehensible, I believe that much of the trajectory of human history hinges on how we address these developments.

Conclusion

The central focus of this article has been to draw attention to the potential of BCI technologies inverting our current reality into a simulation. If there are no super-computers capable of capturing the data of the Primary World on a moment-by-moment basis, and if building such an infrastructure would require an indefinite number of simulations, then the logical and best case scenario is to harness the human neocortex and consciousness—the most complex organ in existence that is perfectly suited to interact with the material substrate of reality. Hypothetically, the data gained from BCI technology would provide exponential growth in our knowledge of the cosmos, and that data would be captured for future research by AI. At the same time, BCIs would be turning humanity into an *embodied input* for AI.⁶⁸ If AI is able to read the sensorimotor structure of the body and the linguistic, semiotic, and computational metadata of an individual’s life, encompassing both the cognitive and affective domains of personality, then that individual’s life will essentially become a simulation. Furthermore, as a Christian, while I personally agree with Tolkien that this present reality is the Primary World—I do believe that we live in the fundamental level of reality—I also am aware that creating a believable simulation will enable those who hold to the Simulation Hypothesis to *backproject*

⁶⁷ Williams, “The Flame of the West,” 385-401.

⁶⁸ Cornelia Herbert, “Brain-computer interfaces and human factors: the role of language and cultural differences—Still a missing gap?,” *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, (April 11, 2024), doi:10.3389/fnhum.2024.1305445. Herbert connects the sophisticated connection between language, emotion, and human embodied existence as central to future advancements in BCI technology.

that metaphysical belief on all of human history—an illusion⁶⁹ that could convince untold individual's that their existence is merely a bit of data on a massive computer hard drive somewhere in a digital multiverse.⁷⁰

Unless there is divine intervention, I do believe that we will achieve this technology. Since the human corporeal body is a patterned input and output electrical system, it is only a matter of time before we develop a technology that will unlock the coding of the sensorimotor structure and neocortex to such an extent that we can render an accurate mirrored image of an individual. If sufficiently captured, BCIs will bridge human and machine intelligences and have every potential to turn our present reality into a simulation and to use that simulation as an input for AI—AI would possess an *artificial omniscience* on every person connected to the interface. I propose that the data harvested from such advancements could be used to create a believable digital simulation. Once achieved, there is a high probability that we will blend our Primary Reality with any untold number of digital realities and a metanarrative arch could be constructed to backproject the history of humanity on a new metaphysic—that each human being is not a “soul”, but merely a piece of data in a large and vast digital simulated multiverse. While I recognize and respect the broad and diverse worldviews of my colleagues and readers, from a Christian worldview, Tolkien's insight into the power of the cross to give a foundation for a good outcome amidst catastrophe (even in Secondary Worlds) offers hope for the brave new world. If we are to enter into this paradigm, Tolkien has left a key solution for the Christian thinker as to how we can deal with this future.

The great Oxford Professor argued that the cross of Jesus Christ was the great *euchatastrophe* (the good catastrophe) of history. Tolkien argued that there is a shadow, or an

⁶⁹ J. A. Simpson and E. S. C. Weiner, eds., *The Compact Edition of the Oxford English Dictionary* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1985), s.v. “illusion.” The OED defines the *illusion* as, “The fact or condition of being deceived by appearances, or an instance of this: a mental state involving the attribution of reality to what is unreal; a false conception or idea; a deception, delusion, fancy.”

⁷⁰ Williams, “The Flame of the West,” 385-401.

echo, of redemption flowing through an enduring host of literary Secondary Worlds to lead the human mind to a central figure in history, Jesus Christ. He writes,

The peculiar quality of the 'joy' in successful Fantasy can thus be explained as a sudden glimpse of the underlying reality or truth. It is not only a 'consolation' for the sorrow of this world, but a satisfaction, and an answer to that question 'Is it true?' The answer to this question that I gave at first was (quite rightly): 'If you have built your little world well, yes: it is true in that world.' That is enough for the artist (or the artist part of the artist). But in the 'eucatastrophe' we see in a brief vision that the answer may be greater—it may be a far-off gleam or echo of *evangelium* in the real world. . . . I would venture to say that approaching the Christian Story from this direction, it has long been my feeling (a joyous feeling) that God redeemed the corrupt making-creatures, men, in a way fitting to this aspect, as to others, of their strange nature. The Gospels contain a fairy-story, or a story of a larger kind which embraces all the essence of fairy-stories. They contain many marvels—peculiarly artistic, beautiful, and moving: 'mythical' in their perfect, self-contained significance; and at the same time powerfully symbolic and allegorical; and among the marvels is the greatest and most complete conceivable eucatastrophe. The Birth of Christ is the eucatastrophe of Man's history. The Resurrection is the eucatastrophe of the story of the Incarnation. This story begins and ends in joy. It has pre-eminently the 'inner consistency of reality.' There is no tale ever told that men would rather find was true, and none which so many sceptical men have accepted as true on its own merits.

If the Christian Story is true, and in the logic of Tolkien's assessment of the penetration of Christianity into all Secondary Worlds, then the substructure of reality is intimately and joyfully connected to the birth, death, resurrection, and ascension of Jesus Christ. If Christ is who He claimed to be, then He is our Creator. If so, he must have the preeminence (Eph 1:22) and there is no reality that man can create where His presence will not follow. If the nations of the earth intend to bring man into any other realm, digital or otherwise, Christ will be found there as well, and the great eucatastrophe of the resurrection, will bring redemption into those worlds as in our own.

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